

5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

D1.9 Use Cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM v2.0

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
5G	5th generation
CAM	Connected and Automated Mobility
E2E	End To End
Embb	enhanced Mobile Broadband
ENL	Ericsson Network Location
EU	European Union
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
IPO	Input Process Output
IoT	Internet Of Things
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
Lidar	Light Detection And Ranging
MEC	Mobile Edge Computing
mMTC	massive Machine Type Communications
NTRIP	Networked Transport of RTCM via Internet Protocol
ODD	Operational Design Domain
PI	Performance Indicator
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
RTCM	Radio Technical Commission for Maritime Services
RTK	Real Time Kinematic
UC	Use Case
URLLC	Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications
V2X	Vehicle-to-everything
VRU	Vulnerable Road User

Executive Summary

The 5G-ROUTES project will conduct advanced field trials of most representative and innovative CAM (Connected and Automated Mobility) applications seamlessly functioning across a designated 5G cross-border corridor (Riga-Valga-Tallinn-Helsinki), spanning across 3 EU member states' borders (Latvia-Estonia-Finland) in order to validate the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications under realistic conditions, so as to accelerate the widespread deployment of 5G end-to-end interoperable CAM ecosystems and services in digitised motorways and shipways throughout Europe [1].

The scope of the deliverable D1.9 is to present the use cases, the target KPIs and the high-level test scenarios, which will be tested and validated in field trials across borders. The 5G-ROUTES use cases are organised in two ecosystems: maritime and terrestrial ecosystem.

This report details the methodology, the KPIs and the high-level test scenarios that will be executed to validate 5G-ROUTES use cases. A set of KPIs to assess the technical and business performance has been selected.

In order to assess the technical performance of 5G for the use cases, the KPIs are organised in five categories:

- Throughput
- Latency
- Reliability
- Localisation
- Service Continuity

The maritime ecosystem focuses on the seamless 5G network coverage and continuity of service for the maritime ecosystem: harbours to vessels, and vessels moving at maritime cross-border corridors. The ecosystem addresses 3 use cases:

- UC 5.1 Connected logistics.
- UC 5.2 Live video streaming between ferries and between ferry and harbour at cross border.
- UC 4.1 360° immersive multi-user gaming on the go.

The terrestrial ecosystem addresses both automated vehicle and infotainment use cases. It consists of the following 4 use cases:

- I. See-through platooning. This use case builds on the original use cases UC1.1, UC1.2 and UC1.3 and has the following services: platooning, cooperative lane change and low latency video transmission
- II. Sharing perception and road hazard at the border for connected and automated driving. This use case builds on the original use cases UC2.1, UC3.1 and UC3.3 and has the following services: services: 1) Sensor information sharing for situational awareness 2) Mobile roadwork warning, and 3) Infrastructure assisted advanced driving.
- UC4.1 Infotainment: 360° immersive multi-user gaming on the go.
- UC4.2: 3D Real-time virtual collaboration on the move

Based on analysis of the KPIs for the different use cases, a harmonised set of target KPI values has been selected for assessment of the performance of the 5G system and the CAM Services Platform, which has been developed by 5G-ROUTES.

Different high-level scenarios have been defined for the use cases. For the terrestrial ecosystem, there are two sets of scenarios:

- scenarios to assess service interruption when crossing the border: the use cases use common data traffic profiles. The purpose of the scenarios is to measure service disruption with advanced tools prior to large use case tests.
- scenarios to assess the performance of 5G and the CAM Services platform of 5G-ROUTES for performing the cross-border use cases.

We also defined test scenarios including multi-hop and Satellite backhauling to extend the coverage of 5G systems over sea.

Finally, 4 composite business KPIs have been identified:

- Technological
- Impact assessment
- Financial
- Commercial

The performance indicators which could be used to evaluate these composite business KPIs are detailed and illustrated by examples in this report. They will be dealt with quantitative and qualitative analysis in WP5 Commercialisation, Innovation Management and Standardisation. The business evaluation methodology is described in D1.12 Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results.

1 Introduction

The 5G-ROUTES project aims to conduct advanced field trials of most representative and innovative CAM applications seamlessly functioning across the “Via Baltic-North” 5G cross-border corridor spanning across 3 EU member states borders (Latvia-Estonia-Finland) in order to validate the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications under realistic conditions, so as to accelerate the widespread deployment of 5G E2E interoperable CAM ecosystems and services in digitised motorways and shipways throughout Europe. The definition of innovative use cases is an essential step to develop and exploit CAM service over automotive and maritime platform in the cross-border context.

The present deliverable aims to provide the technical and business KPIs for the 5G cross-border use cases as well as a high-level description of the scenarios to evaluate the 5G related services.

These Use cases related KPIs are different from the so called Agnostic KPIs defined in D1.5, which are related to the intrinsic performance of the network. The Tenant Web portal will collect and process both Use case related KPIs and Agnostic KPIs.

T1.1 provides inputs to other tasks of WP1 and other WPs, regarding the use cases description and requirements to consider in the frame of those tasks and WPs. The work done in this task is summarized in 3 deliverables:

- D1.1 [1] contains an overview of the 5G network characteristics and the detailed description of 5G-ROUTES use cases. It has been delivered in January 2021.
- D1.9, this document, contains the methodology, the KPIs and the test scenarios to assess the performance of 5G-ROUTES use cases.
- D1.2 will provide an update of the use cases, and the KPIs, as they were executed in the field trials of the project.

1.1 Mapping 5G-ROUTES Outputs

Purpose of this section is to map 5G-ROUTES’s Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project’s respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1. Adherence to 5G-ROUTES’s GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

5G-ROUTES GA Component Title	5G-ROUTES GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D1.1 Use cases, scenario, specs & target KPIs for 5G CAM	Use Cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM v1.0	D1.1 Chapter 2, 3 Annex I Annex II	Chapter 2 details the services and architecture of 5G and satellite networks Chapter 3 defines the 3 categories of Use Cases and describes 5G-ROUTES Use Cases Annex I details the responsibility of the partners Annex II details the main external stakeholders of 5G-ROUTES

D1.9 Use cases, scenario, specs & target KPIs for 5G CAM	Use Cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM v2.0	D1.9 Chapter 2, 3, 4	Chapter 2 details the methodology to assess the Use Cases and the selected technical KPIs. Chapter 3 details the test scenarios Chapter 4 details the business KPIs
TASKS			
T1.1 Definition and detailed analysis of CAM use cases, scenarios, specifications for technological enablers and target KPIs (technological and business)	<p>The aim of this task is to capture the requirements from the end-user CAM stakeholders, including the articulation of detailed use case scenarios and usability needs, and relevant target technological and business KPIs, which will be validated in the field trials.</p> <p>Integrated satellite/terrestrial architectures and interfaces between traffic flow from satellite operator and MNO core network will also be defined in this task.</p> <p>This task will be divided into two key sub tasks:</p> <p>(a) systematic compilation of current use cases features and capabilities (b) requirement analysis.</p> <p>A requirement capture will involve the documentation of CAM end-users needs and opinions about new innovative vertical use cases that require 5G performance capabilities in the domains of automotive, railways, transport & logistics, IoT and infotainment.</p> <p>Such use cases will be mapped to specific target KPI and SLA values (e.g., throughput, mobility, latency, density, reliability, positioning accuracy, coverage, service provisioning time, QoS, QoE, etc.), which will set the baseline for conducting the actual measurements during the field trials.</p>	<p>D1.1 Chapter 3</p> <p>D1.9 Chapter 2</p> <p>D1.9 Chapter 4</p> <p>D1.9 Chapter 5</p>	<p>The systematic compilation of current use cases features, and capabilities is done in chapter 3</p> <p>The requirement analysis, including end users' needs, will lead to the definition of the test facilities, test scenarios and KPIs (subtask b)</p> <p>Definition of the methodology and selection of technical KPIs</p> <p>Definition of target KPIs, SLA and test scenarios</p> <p>Definition of business KPIs to assess the use cases from a business perspective</p>

1.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The document is structured as follows:

- Chapter 1 contains a general description of the content of this document and its relevance to 5G-ROUTES expected outputs.
- Chapter 2 defines the methodology, the process for calculation of the KPIs and the set of technical performance KPIs.
- Chapter 3 gives an overview of the use cases.
- Chapter 4 details the target KPIs and the high-level test scenarios for the different use cases.
- Chapter 5 details business KPIs and associated performance indicators.
- Chapter 6 concludes the report.

1.3 Linkage to Other Deliverables

D1.1 details the use cases and their specification as well as the target KPIs. This deliverable provides a refinement of the KPIs for both the technical performance assessment as well as for the business validation. This deliverable also includes the high-level test scenarios for each of the use cases.

The deliverable is related to D1.12, where the test framework is specified, as well as to deliverable D1.5 where the network level PIs and their measurement is specified.

The following types of KPIs can be identified in the 5G-ROUTES project:

- **Network level performance indicators (PI)**, which are agnostic to the use cases. The targets for these network PIs are determined so that the use case target PIs can be fulfilled. These PIs and their measurements are described in D1.5 “Methodologies for cross-border collaboration and validation of 5G features for CAM v1.0”. The KPIs will be selected from the measured performance indicators and described in D1.6 “Methodologies for cross-border collaboration and validation of 5G features for CAM v2.0”.
- **use case specific KPIs**. This deliverable will describe both the use case specific **technical KPIs** and the **business KPIs** for the ecosystems. The framework for collecting and analysing the data is described in D1.12 “Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results v2.0”.

This deliverable will also provide a brief description of the test scenarios, which will be described in more detail in deliverable D4.1 “Planning, setup and operational management handbook”.

The use cases will be trialled, and the technical performance evaluated in WP4, and the business validation will be performed in WP5. The technical KPIs, measured during the trials, will be visualised in the Tenant Web Portal, which implements the method described in this deliverable. The Tenant Web Portal is described in D2.7.

Deliverable D1.2 will give a final update of this document, based on the experiences from the field trials.

Figure 1: Linkage between WP1 deliverables

2 KPI Methodology

Several use cases illustrating the interest of 5G networks have been defined in 5G-ROUTES project. Each use case has particular requirements towards the 5G infrastructure. To validate the benefits of 5G and the technical enablers for each use case, a number of test scenarios will be executed during the 5G-ROUTES project to assess the impact of 5G and the 5G-ROUTES solutions on service performance.

2.1 5G-ROUTES KPI Methodology

A wide range of potential KPIs can be defined to measure the performance of the use cases in a 5G environment. 5G-ROUTES has developed a method for the selection and grouping and scoring of the KPIs.

KPIs are generally defined as a set of orthogonal PIs representative of important aspects of a system. The number of KPIs must remain small (less than 10) to ensure a proper orthogonality between the indicators and facilitate the analysis.

5G-ROUTES developed and assessed an innovative method for assessing the satisfaction level of a use case. Key to this method is the concept of a “Composite KPI”. As for traditional KPIs, the objective is to give an indication of the performance of the system in particular situations. But instead of a simple arbitrary selection of KPIs to represent the system, we combine the results of several performance indicators in a single Composite KPI. The value of the Composite KPI is the satisfaction level expressed in percentage. These values can be displayed in a spider diagram.

In this method, KPIs are grouped in several categories (e.g., latency, throughput, reliability, localisation...). For each of these categories, several representative Performance Indicators are selected (e.g., for latency the median end-to-end latency, the 95% end-to-end latency). For each of these values two thresholds are defined: a target value (good) and value corresponding to the poorest allowed performance (bad). Following the measured value of the Performance Indicator, an acceptance value is issued: 100% for good, 0% for bad, and 50% in between the good and bad values. Consequently, a Composite Key indicator for the category is calculated as the average of the acceptance values for the selected Performance Indicators.

This method was implemented in the Tenant Web Portal and benchmarked during the first set of lab trials. The method has however a set of shortcomings:

- High dependency on the thresholds identified by the experts. Setting threshold values for services is not an easy task: when comparing literature for the target KPIs for specific services, there may be large differences in the values suggested, and the need for two values makes it even more complex.
- Difficulty to make statistical analysis for Composite Key indicators. This could be improved by changing the calculation of the Composite Key Indicator, but fails if the obtained values are either all good or bad.

Therefore the method was simplified for the technical performance assessment, using only one target for the KPI instead of two acceptance values and using the composite key indicators only for visualisation of the results. For the selection of technical KPIs, literature such as the 5GPP White Paper on ICT-19 performance KPIs [2] is used. The selection of target values for the KPIs is based on a literature study of comparable use cases. For instance, both 3GPP [14] and 5GAA [15],[20],[21] have analysed several use cases and their service level requirements.

2.2 KPI Calculation Process

The KPI calculation process is common to all use cases, and consists of the following steps

- For each use case, one or more test scenarios are defined to test the impact of 5G functionalities and the enablers, developed in the 5G-ROUTES project, under particular/critical circumstances.
- A test scenario will consist of a number of experiments which are repeated under identical conditions (e.g., same weather conditions, some test route).

- Measurements are performed, at different control points, and the data are stored. The data which are stored during the experiments are identified in D1.12.
- For each of the experiments, the measurements are analysed, and Performance Indicators are calculated from the measurements.
- The most important Performance Indicators, selected by the use case responsible, are then fed as KPIs into the Tenant Web Portal, where they are visualised.
- The KPIs are grouped in different categories, which are:
 - Throughput
 - Latency
 - Reliability
 - Localisation
 - Service continuity
- For each of these categories a composite KPI is calculated for visualisation of the experiment result:
 - for each of the KPIs in a group the satisfaction level is calculated (0, 100%),
 - Finally, the Composite KPI satisfaction level is calculated as the average of the satisfaction levels of the KPIs in the category. The composite KPI is expressed as percentage and can be displayed in a spider diagram.
- Based on the KPIs for the different experiments of a scenario, aggregated values are calculated for the scenario KPI.. The composite indicators will be visualised both for single experiments, as well as for the aggregated experiments. Statistical analysis is performed on the KPIs, not on the composite KPIs.

2.3 Selection of Technical Performance KPIs

The KPIs to be monitored during the project have been selected because of their importance for the use case and their relation to 5G technology. For the selection of KPIs, literature such as the 5GPP White Paper on ICT-19 performance KPIs [2] is used.

Five main KPI categories have been selected to evaluate the use cases:

- Throughput
- Latency
- Reliability
- Localisation
- Service continuity

2.3.1 KPIs for Throughput, Latency, Reliability and Localisation

Throughput is critical for eMBB applications. The related Performance Indicator is:

- **User experienced data rate:** The number of correctly received bits contained in the service data units per unit of time (bit/s or bps).

Latency is particularly critical for URLLC applications. Latency can be measured at several control points., both at link/transport level and at application level. Related Performance Indicators include:

- **End-to-end (communication) latency:** Elapsed time from the moment a data packet is transmitted by the source application to the moment it is received by the destination application instance(s) [18].
- **Round Trip Time (RTT):** Time it takes for a data packet to be sent to a destination plus the time it takes for an acknowledgment of that packet to be received back at the origin.
- **User perceived end-to-end latency:** this includes the end-to-end latency, as well as the processing time both at transmission and receiver, e.g., the time delay between a video representation and the source.
- **One-way latency** for a single link, measured with a passive measurement tool (e.g., Qosium) between two IP-addresses. Latencies for upload and download can be distinct.

Reliability is particularly critical for URLLC application. Relevant performance indicators:

- **(Service) reliability:** Ratio of messages which is passed successfully (e.g., end-to-end latency within a predefined time limit) between the actors, within the specified range of the service. This definition is hence tightly coupled to the end-to-end latency, e.g., target of a 95% end-to-end latency at 100 ms is comparable to a reliability of 95% for a reliability with as time limit criterion 100 ms.
- **Packet data loss:** relevant PI for measurements at link/transport level for a specific link. For TCP/IP traffic, at application level, all packets are normally delivered.
- **Quality of Experience (QoE):** The overall acceptability of a service, as perceived subjectively by the end user (definition from ITU-T).
- **Quality of Service (QoS):** QoS may imply a list of PIs that need to be fulfilled e.g., RTT latency < 10ms AND Reliability > 99.999%

Localisation is critical for CAM use cases. This category addresses the calculation of the UE position, using self-localisation technologies (e.g., using GNSS and RTK) or 5G technologies, but also Relevant Performance Indicators:

- **Positioning accuracy:** Positioning accuracy refers to the closeness of a measured location, to the real location of the device at the time of the measurement (as measured with RTK-GNSS).

Service Continuity. For cross-border scenarios, the continuity of the service when moving from one network provider to another is critical. The relevant Performance Indicators are indicated in the next section.

Although the generic Composite KPIs are common to all 5G routes use cases, the respective KPIs depend on the use cases and is detailed in Section 3.

2.3.2 KPIs for Service Continuity

5G-ROUTES pays specific attention to border crossings, and hence roaming related events are of special interest for 5G-ROUTES.

Handover has three main phases: preparation, execution and completion. The handover procedure starts with an event at the UE generating a measurement report to the source gNB. This measurement report results in a Handover request from the gNB to the target gNB. For intra-network handover, the RRC connection reconfiguration message acts as a handover command, starting the execution phase. At that moment the user-plane traffic interrupts, and the source gNB forwards the traffic to the target gNB, which buffers the packets. The handover ends after the UE sends a handover confirm (RRC Configuration complete) message to the target gNB and the UE receives the first data packet from the target gNB.

Figure 2: User plane interruption during handover (based on [17])

Based on this process, the following KPIs are defined at control level:

- **Handover preparation time:** time between the measurement report by the UE, triggering the handover, until the start of handover execution (RRC Connection Reconfiguration) event. For intra-network handover this causes only minimal delay, but in case of roaming there may be considerable delays, and during this time the performance of the network may be poor.
- **Mobility Interruption Time:** The time duration during which a user terminal cannot exchange user plane Packets with any base station (or other user terminal) during transitions. This is defined as the time difference between RRC Connection Reconfiguration and New Data Receive messages.

In a Local Breakout configuration, the UE application has then to connect to the network functions in the new network. This means, that for enablers and CAM services deployed in the CAM Services Platform, developed by 5G-ROUTES, which is implemented near the edge or the core of the 5G network, the UE application has to start reconnecting to the services in the new network.

In the case of CAM services, which follow the UE, these have to be re-instantiated in the new network. This is done prior to the border crossing.

Hence, two additional KPIs are defined:

- **Service startup time after handover:** the time between the end of handover and the availability of the service.
- **CAM Service instantiation time:** the time needed for instantiating a CAM service in the CAM Services Platform, from the moment the activation command is sent until the acknowledgement that the CAM service is installed. The larger the duration of CAM service instantiation, the earlier the CAM service has to be instantiated, and how larger the inaccuracy whether and when the UE will cross the border.

For the complete service, the following KPIs can be determined at service level:

- **Service Interruption Time:** Duration during which the application does not exchange information during handover situations (e.g., end-to-end latency within a predefined limit). The service interruption time is hence the sum of: handover preparation time¹, mobility interruption time and service startup time.

¹ Service interruption time is measured at application level. At application level, the 5G measurement events (A1-A5, B1-B2) cannot be measured. As start of the handover preparation time the moment when the measured latency exceeds a predefined threshold.

- **Application-Level Handover Success Rate:** Applies to scenarios where an active application-level session (e.g., communication between application client at UE/OBU and the Application Server) needs to be transferred from a source to a destination application instance (e.g., located at MEC hosts at the source and destination networks respectively) because of a cross-border mobility event. The KPI describes the ratio of successfully completed application-level handovers i.e., where service provisioning is correctly resumed/ continued past the network level handover, from the new application instance [19] within a predefined time limit.

Figure 3 shows an example of service interruption at cross border in 5G NSA network in a Home Routing scenario (tests of UC3.2 in Bikernieki). The triggering event is the measurement report, but it takes 12 seconds before the actual handover (and user plane interruption) takes place. As no network services are used in this example, there is no service startup time, and the total service interruption time is 37 seconds.

Figure 3: Example of a cross-border handover event between 5G NSA networks

Another special case is related to RTK-correction signals, which may be provided from NTRIP (Networked Transport of RTCM via Internet Protocol) servers or from the 5G network through the ENL (Ericsson Network Location) service.

- **RTK correction interruption time:** interval during which the UE does not have access to the RTK correction signal when crossing the border.

The service continuity category also includes coverage, defined as:

- **coverage:** percentage of the pilot area which has radio access

3 Use Case Ecosystems

3.1 Introduction

The different use cases in 5G-ROUTES, which were introduced in D1.1 [1], have been grouped into two ecosystems. The main purpose of the grouping is to sharpen the focus of the work performed in 5G-ROUTES, and to group use cases which are, in essence, dealing with the same issues.

- Terrestrial Ecosystem – the major issue addressed is the service continuity of services for supporting connected and automated driving and for infotainment services, offered to users crossing borders.
- Maritime Ecosystem – the major issue being addressed in this ecosystem is the seamless 5G network coverage and continuity of service for the maritime ecosystem: harbours to vessels, and vessels moving at maritime cross-border corridors.

The use cases in the ecosystems have common objectives and will be trialled in the same test environment. Through combining the use cases in these two ecosystems, efforts in trials and in test logistics can be reduced.

3.2 Terrestrial Ecosystem

3.2.1 Introduction

The terrestrial ecosystem from 5G-ROUTES addresses road use cases and involves both connected and automated driving across borders and infotainment use cases. As current sensing technologies used for Advanced driver-assistance systems (ADAS) encounter limitations due to their limited range, possible occlusion, imprecision in the measurement, data sharing between road entities (vehicles, road infrastructure) though reliable connectivity link is a primary requirement to support automated driving in the road transport network. Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication is an important lever to extend vehicles operational design domain (ODD) by and promote safe and efficient transportation through automated driving. With the release 16, 3GPP has introduced enhancements to support V2X services with 5G networks. Such services can benefit from enablers such as slicing, edge computing, network function virtualization to provide low latency and high reliability.

The use cases in the terrestrial ecosystem demonstrate the improved capabilities of 5G across borders. The vehicles and end-user devices interact with virtualized CAM service backends, which are deployed in the CAM Services Platform, which is being developed in 5G-ROUTES, on edge or cloud points of presence of the network. Ensuring low end-to-end latency is a major requirement for automated driving support use cases to guarantee road safety.

The terrestrial ecosystem consists of 4 use cases, which are based on the original UC1-4, which are described in D1.1:

- I. **See-through platooning** (based on UC1.1, UC1.2 and UC1.3);
- II. **Sharing perception and road hazard at the border for connected and automated driving** (based on UC2.1, UC3.1 and UC3.3);
- III. **Infotainment:**
 - UC4.1: 360° immersive multi-user gaming on the go;
 - UC4.2 3D Real-time virtual collaboration on the move.

The combination of the original use cases was motivated by a more efficient use of project resources. Several use cases share common features, such as similar data communication patterns (e.g., V2X messages in use case II) and use of CAM services.

3.2.2 High-Level Project Architecture Overview

The 5G-ROUTES architecture is described in more in detail in D7.3 [24], and is shown in Figure 4. Only the main principles of the architecture, which affect the use case scenarios and testing are described here.

Figure 4: 5G-ROUTES Project architecture

The main components of the architecture are:

- 5G-ROUTES communication networks in Latvia and Estonia. The core is realised by TTU in Tallinn, and the network has an edge site in Valga/Valka. For handover between networks, Local Breakout is used.
- The 5G-ROUTES CAM Services platform, consisting of:
 - enablers, which have been developed in 5G-ROUTES WP2, and are described in D2.1 [25] and D2.9 [26]. The enablers are either deployed at the core and/or the edge. The enablers serve the following functionalities:
 - provide CAM service lifecycle management: onboarding, instantiation, termination and service relocation to offer service continuity when virtualised CAM service backends needs to be instantiated when users cross the border.
 - support low-latency communication between UEs (V2X message routing service).
 - support situational awareness (object data fusion for improved situational awareness).
 - support use case setup and logging (Tenant Web Portal).
 - CAM services, which deploy use case specific services. The CAM services are of two types:
 - “Follow-me” CAM services, which follow a fleet of UEs guided by a leader UE when crossing the border and are instantiated in the available points of presence of the new network and thanks to the use of Local Breakout roaming configuration, they can still benefit from low-latency communications in the new domain. This type of services is piloted in use cases 1, UC4.1 and UC4.2.

- “Location-fixed” CAM services, which provide location specific data to the UE. Those services rely on the cross-domain communication mechanisms of the CAM Services Platform, namely the V2X message routing service to reach the user and obtain information of neighbouring domains. When the UE crosses the border, a similar service has to communicate using the same protocols with the UE. This type of services is piloted in use case II. In this use case, road services which consist in the sharing of geographically relevant information (measurements from on-board and roadside sensors, hazardous events notification) interact in real-time with automated vehicles. Following the 3GPP specifications, they can be deployed on top of the 5G core network and be accessible using the Uu reference point. In a border crossing situation, as a vehicle changes from a home to a visited network, network access can be interrupted, leading to stopping data exchange with such road services.

3.2.3 Use Case Descriptions

3.2.3.1 See-Through Platooning

Introduction

This use case is based on the original use cases:

- UC1.1 Dynamic vehicles platooning.
- UC1.2 Cooperative lane change.
- UC1.3 See-through view for safe automated overtake.

The use case demonstrates the use of Follow-me type of CAM services, which are instantiated when the vehicle crosses the border.

Description

The objective of the use case is to demonstrate how CAM services, deployed in the CAM Services platform, which is developed in 5G-ROUTES, can be used to support drivers when moving across borders. Demonstrated support functions are platooning for automated vehicles supported by see-through video transmission as well as remote support to the drivers.

In the platooning sub use-case (UC1.1), the objective is to implement a system for automated vehicles to dynamically form a platoon with harmonized speeds, following a piloting vehicle. By using a combination of sensors and communication, the aim is to reduce inter-vehicular distances to a safe minimum while also supporting border crossing and providing a radar-based fallback mechanism.

During the platoon, vehicles can perform automated lane change manoeuvres (UC1.2), while also taking into account the intentions of other vehicles. By using a combination of sensors and communication, movements of the vehicles are coordinated in a way that reduces unnecessary changes in speed and keeps the drivers safe, while also supporting border crossing scenarios.

The see-through capability (UC1.3) gives the (safety) driver of a vehicle in a platoon a view of the traffic situation in front of the leading vehicle. The main objective of this sub-use case is to provide enhanced visibility of road awareness during platooning and for safe automated manoeuvres. The objective is to support the driver to make decisions when there is a need to leave the platoon.

The combination of these automotive use-cases offers a more holistic trial covering several cross-border issues, such as seamless communication of vehicle data and high-bandwidth video streaming across the border and seamless support of drivers across borders.

Demonstration Scenario

For demonstration, a scenario has been built, combining features of the different use cases. The scenario consists of the following phases:

- Platoon is formed with 3 vehicles (UC1.1).
- The vehicle in front of the platoon starts streaming video to the other vehicles in the platoon (UC1.3).
- The platoon starts driving along the road towards the border (UC1.1).
- The second vehicle plans a manoeuvre, e.g., selects an exit on the motorway, and plans to leave the platoon (UC1.2). The second vehicle performs the lane change manoeuvre automatically (or manually). The third vehicle is informed and forms the platoon with the first vehicle when the second vehicle has changed lanes.
- When crossing the border, all services (platoon, video transmission, game/meeting) continue without disruption.
- The video reception stops when the second vehicle has left the platoon or when the front vehicle stops transmission.

Cross-Border 5G Aspects and Main Research Questions

The main challenges related to cross border 5G are:

- The services offered to the vehicle (platooning, video transmission, gaming) should continue when crossing the border without disruption.
- The use cases use virtualised CAM services, which follow the users, and should be instantiated in the visiting network.
- Sufficient resources should be reserved for V2X services, guaranteeing low latency for time critical functionalities, also when crossing borders.
- Availability of 5G position enhancing at both sides of the border, assuring sufficiently good accuracy for automated driving.

From the previous challenges, the main hypotheses are derived:

- The 5G SA test networks and the 5G-ROUTES enablers allow seamless handover and continuity for the service, respectively.
- The 5G-ROUTES enablers allow to instantiate the virtualised CAM services in the visiting network in time to guarantee seamless service continuity.
- Slicing availability ensures network resource availability when crossing borders to achieve the target KPIs related to latency and throughput.
- High positioning accuracy for supporting automated driving is available at both sides of the border.
- Different live video sources streamed on the same network do not collide or overload the network bandwidth capacity.

CAM Services and 5G Specific Elements

For the see-through functionality, the use case uses a video proxy CAM service, which shares the video between the different vehicles.

In addition, the use case uses a platoon management service, which keeps track of the status of the different vehicles within the platoon. Slicing is used to provide specific resources for V2X information (containing data like position and speed of the vehicles).

Enablers

The use case makes use of the following 5G-ROUTES enablers:

- Integration Fabric.
- Tenant Web Portal for use case setup and logging.
- CAM Repository for instantiation of the CAM services.

- V2X Message Routing service for exchanging the V2X vehicle status information.
- Assisted Service Continuity for CAM Services.
- Predictive Resource Allocation of V2X Related Network Functions.

3.2.3.2 *Sharing perception and road hazard at the border for connected and automated driving*

Introduction

This use case combines the use cases for road safety and situation awareness where virtual services are of location-fixed type. It is based on a combination of the functionalities of the use cases for connected and automated driving, described in D1.1:

- UC2.1 Real-time traffic info and cooperative intersection collision control.
- UC3.1 Sensor info sharing for cooperative situation awareness.
- UC3.3 Vulnerable Road User (VRU) collision avoidance.

Description

A common feature between these use cases is that they involve CAM services which are disseminating data packets towards road users (vehicles, cyclists, pedestrians...) through the V2X Message Routing enabler to ensure safety and continuity of traffic related information during border crossing. A common requirement is hence that the service continuity has to be assured when crossing borders to maintain a high-level of availability in the automated driving functionalities by ensuring that a CAV can quickly respond to any unlikely event. As vehicles are driving in mixed conditions, i.e., where vehicles from both sides of the countries are sharing the same driving environment, similar information must be disseminated on both sides.

Demonstration Scenario

A demonstration scenario combining features of the different use cases has been built. It highlights how the CAM services deployed by the individual use cases are contributing to increase the awareness about hazardous situation and driving conditions of a connected and automated vehicle during its journey from one country to the second one. In particular, the scenario demonstrated the following services: 1) Perception sharing between multiple vehicles 2) Mobile roadwork warning, 3) Infrastructure based driving assistance in complex zones (e.g., intersection area).

Figure 5: Illustration of Use Case II demonstration scenario

The scenario consists of the following phases:

1. A CAV is driving towards the border. It receives data packets from the 5G network including location and speed of other connected vehicles. This information is needed to extend the field of view of its on-board sensors, hence, allowing automated driving at a high speed. (UC3.1)
2. Close to the border, CAV also benefits from a CAM service for sharing perception from infrastructure sensors and sending traffic related information (road alerts or traffic light status). Hence, it can anticipate the road condition after the border and adapt its behaviour. (UC 2.1)
3. A mobile roadwork is active after the border, a specific information is triggered and sent to the CAV. (UC 3.3)
4. When the vehicle crosses the border, it detects changes in the networking conditions, on-board applications monitor these changes and reconnect to the V2X Message Routing enabler.
5. Mobile roadwork information is being regularly updated (e.g., location of the roadwork area), the vehicle can be notified of these updates when continuity of the network service is maintained.

Cross-Border 5G Aspects and Main Research Questions

The different use cases have the following common challenges:

- The services offered to the vehicle users (e.g., mobile roadwork warning, infrastructure perception) should be available on both sides of the border thanks to the V2X Message Routing enabler and accessible when crossing the border without disruption.
- The use cases using CAM services (e.g., infrastructure perception, mobile roadworks warning for CAD), should be able to disseminate information to both sides of the border.
- Slicing allows to reserve resources for V2X services, guaranteeing low latency for time critical functionalities, also when crossing borders.
- Availability of 5G positioning enhancing at both sides of the border, assuring sufficiently good accuracy for automated driving.

From these challenges, the main hypotheses are derived:

- The 5G SA test networks and the 5G-ROUTES enablers allow seamless handover and continuity of the service.
- Slicing availability ensures network resource availability when crossing borders in order to achieve the target KPIs related to latency and reliability for different types of user equipment (vehicles & cyclist OBUs, road agent devices, roadside infrastructure router).
- High positioning accuracy for supporting automated driving is available at both sides of the borders.

CAM Services and 5G Specific Elements

- The use case has “location-fixed” type of CAM services for providing collision warning with mobile road-work operation, and for the infrastructure based driving assistance.

Enablers

The use case makes use of the following 5G-ROUTES enablers:

- Integration Fabric.
- Tenant Web Portal for use case setup and logging.
- CAM Repository for instantiation of the CAM services.
- V2X Message Routing service for exchanging the V2X vehicle status information.

3.2.3.3 Infotainment: 360° Immersive Multi-User Gaming on the Go (UC4.1)

Description and Demonstration Scenario

This use case aims to implement a cross-border proof system for collaborative augmented reality gaming. The use case will be demonstrated both in road conditions (e.g., users travelling in a single vehicle or a platoon) and in maritime conditions, in a ferry.

The users of the game share a collaborative gaming experience via their mobile phones, i.e., the devices are connected to a game server, deployed in the 5G core, devices share continuously their location, device orientation and players’ interactions. At the same time the server processes players’ data in real time and responds back to the devices with the composed game scene. Hence, the common set of game dynamics is shared to promote a collaborative gaming experience.

Cross-Border 5G Aspects and Main Research Questions

The main challenges related to cross border 5G are:

- The gaming services should continue when crossing the border without disruption.
- The use cases use a virtualised CAM service, which follow the users, and should be instantiated in the visiting network.

From the previous challenges, the main hypotheses are derived:

- the 5G SA test networks and 5G-ROUTES enablers allow seamless handover and continuity of the service, respectively;
- the real-time game service can be deployed and used successfully on an edge server;
- users’ game information can be exchanged between the servers in an interoperable way, also across borders;
- slicing availability ensures network resource availability when crossing borders in order to achieve the target KPIs related to latency and reliability for smart devices

CAM Services and 5G Specific Elements

In the road scenario, the game server is implemented as a VNF deployed with the CAM Services platform. For the ferry scenario, the CAM service is installed in the cloud.

Enablers

The use case makes use of the following 5G-ROUTES enablers:

- Integration Fabric.
- Tenant Web Portal for use case setup and logging.
- CAM Repository for instantiation of the CAM services.
- V2X Message Routing Service: for exchange of the V2X user device (laptop) location status information.
- Assisted Service Continuity for CAM Services.
- Predictive Resource Allocation of V2X Related Network Functions.

3.2.3.4 Infotainment: 3D Real-Time Virtual Collaboration on the Move (UC4.2)

Description and Demonstration Scenario

The use case focuses on a virtual reality application, where users use a VR headset and laptop connected to a 5G network to participate in an immersive meeting session. In the different locations the presenter is captured in front of a green screen and embedded in a virtual environment, which is streamed to the multicast streaming server deployed in the core/edge. The audience (e.g., passengers in a vehicle) sees the VR stream (4K/8K video data) and is allowed to interact with the details in the immersive scene. At the same time the audience can verbally communicate with the presenter.

Cross-Border 5G Aspects and Main Research Questions

The main challenges related to cross border 5G are:

- the virtual collaboration service should continue when crossing the border without disruption;
- the use cases use a virtualised CAM service, which follow the users, and should be instantiated in the visiting network.

From the previous challenges, the main hypotheses are derived:

- the 5G SA test networks and 5G-ROUTES enablers allow seamless handover and continuity of the service, respectively;
- the virtual collaboration service can be deployed and used successfully on an edge server;
- the 5G-ROUTES enablers allow the video proxy to guarantee seamless service delivery for multiple **users** across borders;
- user's information can be exchanged within the servers in an interoperable way, also across borders;
- slicing availability ensures network resource availability when crossing borders in order to achieve the target KPIs related to bandwidth and reliability.

CAM Services and 5G Specific Elements

Multicast video proxy server deployed in the 5G core/edge. This node distributes the real-time incoming video stream from the presenter to the audience in the vehicles. Viewers can point details of the immersive scene and send voice or data messages to the presenter that are sent directly through a different communication channel than video, so video transmission proxy service communication works unidirectional from source to clients.

Enablers

The use case makes use of the following 5G-ROUTES enablers:

- Integration Fabric.
- Tenant Web Portal for use case setup and for logging.
- CAM Repository for instantiation of the CAM services.
- V2X Message Routing service for exchange of the V2X user device (laptop) location status information.
- Assisted Service Continuity for CAM Services.
- Predictive Resource Allocation of V2X Related Network Functions.

3.3 Maritime Ecosystem

3.3.1 Introduction

This ecosystem aims to explore the combination of several 5G infrastructure solutions to provide seamless connectivity and service continuity in open sea adverse conditions. The focus is to use a ferry as a test platform to establish the quality of service and continuity trials and tests on the operational ferry and to study what opportunities 5G could enable for maritime connectivity and communication (services and technology improvements). The ecosystem will develop and test solutions for maritime transportation and different stakeholders and customer groups for this kind of logistic, especially in cross border and international maritime corridors. The main stakeholder group is ferry operators, who are seeking new (communication) services and quality for their customers: passengers, freight transport, 3rd party value adding services and ports/hubs.

The connectivity reliability in the sea corridor between Estonia and Finland will be tested applying different coordinated connectivity solutions to ensure the continuity of several involved services and related products provided by the following involved use cases:

- UC 4.1 360° immersive multi-user gaming on the go.
- UC 5.1 Connected logistics.
- UC 5.2 Live video streaming between ferries and between ferry and harbour at cross border.

3.3.1.1 Demonstration Scenario

On their journey across the Baltic Sea, ferries encounter significant variations in 5G coverage that forces them to implement a combination of solutions to ensure seamless connectivity. Close to land, the terrestrial base stations in the ports and along the coast are able to provide sufficient bandwidth. With increasing distance to the shore, the signal strength is decreasing and thus alternative connectivity solutions which could enable better coverage and quality of service, such as multi-hop solutions or satellite connectivity need to be considered.

The 5G-ROUTES maritime ecosystem includes terrestrial 700 MHz and 3.5 GHz, and satellite communication for backhaul connectivity and ferry coverage. These scenarios will be extended with the multi-hop connections from the shore and between the vessels. The solutions will be tested and analysed both separately and together. 5G-ROUTES use cases are described so that those cover most of the potential customer and user groups in the ferry, i.e., passengers, freight companies and ferry operators/staff and hence future opportunities and benefits for these user groups can be analysed, so that all users can benefit from the seamless and reliable high-quality communication. Accordingly, studying strategies for load balancing between cellular and satellite backhaul connection will be part of the trials.

In the 5G-ROUTES project the pilot route for the maritime transportation is the link between Helsinki/Finland and Tallinn/Estonia. The planned connectivity trials will be implemented on Eckerö Line's Finbo ferry, which is equipped as a testing platform while travelling on the Baltic Sea. For this purpose, a small cell 5G base station will be installed on the ferry which is working as a moving base station, while the backhauling methods (satellite connectivity, cellular backhaul and multi-hop concepts) with the 5G Core Network of the 5G-ROUTES project shall be tested.

3.3.1.2 Main Research Questions

The main focus in this ecosystem is twofold:

- assuring the availability and coverage of the connectivity over the maritime corridor.
- assuring the quality of the connectivity, e.g., latencies, throughput rates and download speed.

5G-ROUTES studies different connectivity scenarios, which might supplement each other with the vision that 5G will become the primary technology for seamless connectivity in the maritime industry in the near future. In addition to terrestrial network connectivity in ports and near the coast, 5G connectivity through a 5G Multi-Hop

network, as well as 5G using non-terrestrial connectivity in offshore waters is studied. Through these methods of communication, the Quality of Service required for each use case is ensured. Hence the main research questions and hypotheses are:

- the studied solutions provide availability and coverage of connectivity over the whole corridor;
- the quality of the connectivity (latency, throughput, download speed) is sufficient for the use cases.

3.3.2 Use Case Descriptions

This section provides the updated use case descriptions for UC5.1 and UC5.2. The Infotainment use case UC4.1 is tested both in maritime and in terrestrial ecosystem, and is described in section 3.2.3.

3.3.2.1 UC 5.1 Connected Logistics

Updated Description

The use case 5.1 will focus on supply chain transparency in multimodal transportation, which combines road and maritime transportation. The use case consists of two different cases (see Figure 6 below). In the first case, the aim is to enable continuous connection for cargo monitoring IoT systems during the ship trip between Finland and Estonia. Second case will focus on mMTC, and study what opportunities 5G can provide for cargo monitoring and management on logistics nodes such as ports, where in relatively small area density might be high with a lot of active IoT sensors.

Connected logistics use case focuses on how to provide seamless connection for onboard devices and how this connectivity can be utilised for end user solutions and devices. Connected logistics covers two test themes: 1) vehicle-to-backend system connectivity and 2) cybersecurity health reporting.

Theme 1 covers continuous connectivity between Transport Management Systems (TMS) and critical onboard systems, such as vehicle and/or driver health status and remote monitoring for cargo data for critical and secured transportations (CST). CST basic requirement is uninterrupted situational awareness data, ~~i.e.~~ transportation needs to be monitored continuously via remote control tower with video stream and other security sensors to ensure continuous shipment integrity

Theme 2 utilizes new 5G capabilities and onboard device, which can be used to track and monitor positioning metadata and deviations appearing therein. Such analysis can give information about cybersecurity threats and GNSS spoofing.

Both of these themes will follow the same test logic and KPIs, which focus on continuous 5G service availability and quality of service levels. During the trials these aspects will be tested in test drives with:

- service interruption e.g., for upload of cargo integrity data and cybersecurity health data;
- service capacity point of view e.g., for surveillance camera uplink feed;
- service quality.

With available test networks the aim is to test and analyse service continuity in border crossing multi-MNO cases, which is a typical requirement for international logistics and end user solutions. Finally test results will be used to analyse the overall SQL (Structured Query Language), scalability and readiness for logistics end-user services.

Figure 6: Use case 5.1 illustration (source Vediafi).

5G Specific Elements

The use case focuses on maritime transportation that operates between Finland and Estonia. In addition, the case highlights the maritime environment where the communication network quality and coverage are not as good as in on the land area, e.g., in the cities or main roads. In this use case, trials focus on the solution on how to enable continuous and high-quality connection in this maritime transport corridor. The solution will cover combination of various 5G from the shore, multi-hop and satellite connection.

In addition, the use case will utilise new RTK metadata functionalities, which are planned to be enabled with 3GPP rel17, however, now these functionalities can be demonstrated with additional RTK services.

3.3.2.2 UC 5.2 Live video streaming between ferries and between ferry and harbour at cross border

Updated Description

During a trip, the captain of a ferry needs to have a continuous video and speech communication with the ferry's staff and also with the harbour's administration to lead to a safe trip for the passengers and also for the cargo that is transported inside the ferry. Lack of communication between the ferry and its staff at a cross border can possibly lead to human fatalities and damages to ferry. Use case 5.2 focuses on the provision of live streaming services between the captain and the ferry's staff so as a smooth trip can occur throughout the trip including cross border areas. UC 5.2 offers the ability to cover cross-border issues, including seamless communication of high bandwidth video streaming during the multi-hop communication and seamless support to the captain throughout the trip.

5G Specific Elements

This use case 5.2 is an eMBB case, which shares video streaming between the captain, the ferry staff and the harbour administration. In addition, slicing can be used for the provision of specific resources for the communication between the captain and the ferry staff and between the captain and the harbour's administration.

4 Use Case Technical Performance KPIs

4.1 Terrestrial Ecosystem

4.1.1 Harmonised KPIs

In a first phase KPIs were selected for the different use cases within the terrestrial ecosystem. The values for the KPIs were based on analysis of target KPIs set for the use cases in literature by e.g., 5GAA and 3GPP, and by assessment by experts. In a second phase, by comparing the target values set for use cases using similar traffic, the target values for the different use cases were aligned.

- **Throughput: User experienced data rate.** The target value depends on the type of data traffic in the use case. The target value is the highest for video transmission and amounts to 15 Mbps.
For V2X use cases, the messages transmitted are smaller, in the order of 100-1000 bytes transmitted 1-20 times per second, so per vehicle 1-20 kB/s. Assuming up to 50 vehicles in the same area during the trials, the data rate is in the order of 1 Mbps.
- **Latency: communication end-to-end latency: median and 95% percentile**
 - for video transmission, 50 ms is set as target value for the median and 100 ms for the 95% percentile.;
 - for V2X use cases, 20 ms is set as target value for the median and 50 ms for the 95% percentile.
- **Reliability**, defined as the ratio of messages delivered within a specified time limit: the target value is set to 99% for a cut-off time of 100 ms.
- **Localisation**: the location accuracy for automated driving applications is 0.1 m.
- **Service continuity**:
 - **the application level handover success rate** has as target 100%.
 - **service interruption time**: the target value is 0.5 seconds.
 - **CAM service instantiation time**: the target value is 30 seconds. The instantiation time depends on the size and complexity of the CAM service. The instantiation time determines when the service at the latest has to be instantiated prior to the border crossing.
 - **RTK correction interruption time**

Table 2: Harmonised KPIs for the terrestrial ecosystem

KPI category	KPI	target value
Localisation	positioning accuracy	0.1 m
Throughput	user perceived data rate	1 Mbps (V2X) 15 Mbps (video UL/DL)
Latency	end-to-end communication latency (median)	< 20 ms (V2X) 50 ms (video)
	end-to-end communication latency (95% percentile)	50 ms (V2X) 100 ms (video)
Reliability	Reliability (% messages with end-to-latency < 100 ms)	99 %
Service continuity	Application-level Handover success rate	100%
	Service interruption time	0.5 s
	CAM service instantiation time	30 s
	RTK correction interruption time	0 s

4.1.2 Use Case I: See-Through Platooning

4.1.2.1 KPIs

The use case I is based on 3 use cases, which are described in D1.1:

- UC1.1 Dynamic vehicles platooning.
- UC1.2 Cooperative lane change.
- UC1.3 See-through view for safe automated overtake.

Platooning (UC1.1)

For vehicle platooning, the objective is that:

- Following vehicles follow the trajectory of the leading vehicle as closely as possible;
- The distance between the vehicles in the platoon is as small as possible, however sufficiently large to avoid accidents.

In this use-case, 5G enables to enhance the platooning by sending the leading vehicle's state (position, speed, acceleration, steering, etc.) to the following vehicles.

The efficiency of platooning can be measured through KPIs related to the position of the vehicles: the maximum deviation in longitudinal distance between two vehicles and the maximum lateral distances between the trajectory of the leading vehicle and the trajectory of the following vehicle (across track). It should be as small as possible, ideally zero. However, a distance of less than 1 m is acceptable. The target value for the longitudinal distance deviation is 5 m; for the lateral distance deviation 1 m.

The desired throughput depends on message rate and size. The size of the messages is between 100 and 1000 bytes, and is transmitted 10 to 20 times per second, hence the throughput is 1-20 kB/s for a single vehicle.

Regarding end-to-end latency, the objective is to achieve a reaction distance of less than 4 m at 90 km/h, which leads to a minimum reaction time (including vehicle reaction) of 160 ms.

The following considerations were made about service reliability:

- In regular conditions, packet transmission errors can be compensated by redundancy and recovery algorithms (e.g., extrapolation). We will assume that a packet error ratio above 10% is bad, below 5% is good.
- The acceptable service interruption time is between 0 and 1 second.

Table 3: Dynamic Vehicle Platooning KPIs

KPI category	KPI	target value
Localisation	positioning accuracy	0.1 m
	longitudinal distance deviation between 2 vehicles	5 m
	lateral distance between 2 vehicles	1 m
Throughput	user perceived data rate	10 kbps
Latency	end-to-end communication latency (median)	< 20 ms
	end-to-end communication latency (95% percentile)	50 ms
Reliability	Reliability (% messages with end-to-latency < 100 ms)	99 %
Service continuity	Application-level Handover success rate	100%
	Service interruption time	0.5 s
	RTK correction interruption time	0 s

Cooperative Lane Change (UC1.2)

For this functionality, 5G is used for assisted lane-change by sharing relevant state information to the vehicle attempting the manoeuvre. Localisation of the vehicles will be realized via GNSS-RTK and Lidar in addition to radar measurements.

The throughput depends on message rate and size, amounting to 10 kbps per vehicle.

Latency is the time between the emission of the packet by a vehicle and its reception in the vehicle that changes lane. It is measured at application level. The target value is 50 ms.

Reliability is linked to the amount of V2X messages received with an end-to-end latency of less than 100 ms, which is the time between successive V2X messages. The target value is 99%.

The target for the service interruption time is 0.5 seconds.

The following table details the KPIs and their targets.

Table 4: Cooperative Lane Change KPIs

KPI category	KPI	target value
Localisation	positioning accuracy	0.1 m
Throughput	user perceived data rate	10 kbps
Latency	end-to-end communication latency (median)	< 20 ms (V2X)
	end-to-end communication latency (95% percentile)	50 ms
Reliability	Reliability (% messages with end-to-latency < 100 ms)	99 %
Service continuity	Application-level Handover success rate	100%
	Service interruption time	0.5 s
	RTK correction interruption time	0 s

Low-Latency Video Transmission (UC1.3)

This functionality was part of the use case 1.3 “See-through for automated overtaking”, described in D1.1 [1]. The objective of the use case is to facilitate the automated overtaking of a slower moving vehicle through the reception, in the following vehicle of a video taken by the car to be overtaken. A car that wants to overtake a slower vehicle receives a real time stream from the vehicle in front, so that the driver can analyse whether it is safe to overtake. The functionality is used in the platoon to give the drivers of the following vehicle the view in front of the platoon.

Localisation: Localisation accuracy is not critical for video transmission, only during the autonomous overtaking manoeuvre. A localisation accuracy of about 0.1 m is needed for the automated manoeuvre. RTK or a relevant GNSS enhancing technology must be used for supporting automated driving.

Throughput is the user data rate on the air interface, after video compression and before video decompression. The required uplink data rate to transmit the video depends on the configuration of the video streaming. 3GPP [14] requires 10Mbps uplink for video (e.g., 720p video@30fps, MJPEG compression). 5GAA sets as requirement 15 Mbps ((1280*720, 30 Hz)[15]. The value 15 Mbps is set as target.

End-to-end Latency. Two different end-to-end latency values are measured: the end-to-end latency at communication level, measure at transport level between the transmitting and receiving OBU, and the user-experienced latency. User perceived end-to-end Latency is the time between the capture of a video frame and its representation on the Human Machine Interface (HMI) in the vehicle, and hence includes video coding and decoding. The target user experienced latency level is 200 ms, which corresponds at about 10 m for oncoming vehicles at 90 km/h, i.e., the length of 2 vehicles. The target KPI for end-to-end latency at communication level is 50 ms [14][15][16].

Reliability: 5GAA sets as target 99% [15][16] to avoid massive artifacts in the video stream for assisted driving. 3G PP suggests 90% for manual control [14].

Service interruption. As target for the service interruption time when crossing borders 1 second is set. For the CAM service (video proxy) instantiation time a target of 30 seconds is set.

Table 5: See-through View KPIs

KPI category	KPI	target value
Localisation	positioning accuracy (automated overtaking)	< 0.1 m
Throughput	user perceived data rate	>15 Mbps (UL) 15 Mbps (DL)
Latency	user perceived end-to-end latency: from video capture to video representation (median)	< 200 ms
	communication end-to-end latency: from transmission at vehicle UE to receipt at 2 nd UE (median)	< 50 ms
Reliability	Reliability (% with end-to-latency < 100 ms)	99 %
Service continuity	Application-level Handover success rate	100%
	Service interruption time	1 s
	CAM service instantiation time	30 s

4.1.2.2 Scenarios

Scenario 1: Simple Scenario for Service Interruption Testing

In the use case there are two types of data streams:

- 1) video data stream, transmitted from the leading vehicle to the following vehicles.
- 2) V2X data transmitted between vehicles. This consist of small data packages (e.g., CAM messages) which are published by the vehicles in the platoon and received by the other vehicles. The size of the messages is between 100 and 1000 bytes and they are transmitted 10-20 times per second. This type of data stream is also used in use case II.

In addition, the use case makes use of the enablers and a CAM service in the CAM Services platform. The CAM service (video proxy) follows the user equipment (declared leader fleet), and hence has to be instantiated in the second domain when the leader vehicle crosses the border.

Two scenarios are hence developed for evaluating the behaviour of the 5G system and the CAM Services platform in border crossing:

- 1) a UE in a vehicle, transmitting video, interacts with the CAM Services Platform (e.g., V2XBroker and the CAM service (video proxy)). The video is received by another UE, which is installed in the same vehicle. When approaching the border, the CAM service is instantiated in the second network. The first UE crosses the border and connects to the other network and the recent instantiated virtualised CAM service in the second network. The second UE also connects to the second network and receives the video from the CAM service in the second network.
Alternatively, the second UE is replaced with a fixed UE, which can connect to both networks
- 2) for V2X data, the scenario is common with the “simple” scenario for use case II. The main objective is to assess the service interruption time when crossing the border.

Scenario 2: Full Use Case Scenario

The objective of this scenario is to assess the performance of 5G and the CAM Services Platform when a platoon of vehicles crosses the border to the other network. The test scenarios for evaluation of the 5G functionalities include:

- platoon consisting of 2 vehicles crossing the border (UC1.1)
- platoon of vehicles performing lane change manoeuvre in the border area (UC1.2)
- video transmission between 2 vehicles following each other across the border (UC1.3).

The use of slicing will be evaluated, with one slice for the V2X traffic and one slice for the video transfer.

More information on the test scenarios will be provided in D4.1.

4.1.3 Use Case II: Sharing perception and road hazard at the border for connected and automated driving

The use case is based on three different functionalities:

- 1) Sensor information sharing for situation awareness
- 2) Infrastructure assisted advanced driving
- 3) Collision warning with mobile roadwork operation

4.1.3.1 KPIs

Sensor Information Sharing for Cooperative Situation Awareness

In the sensor info sharing for cooperative situation awareness, vehicles exchange information related to objects detected by the vehicle sensors. Data on the observed objects is sent as a CPM (Cooperative Perception Message) message to the V2X Message Routing service and dispatched to the other cars in the neighbourhood.

For the Sensor info sharing for cooperative situation awareness relevant KPIs are:

Localisation accuracy: the target accuracy for the vehicle position is 0.1 m [14]. High accuracy is required in order to avoid collisions between (automated) vehicles, and for assuring the performance of data fusion: the absolute position of the object is calculated from the position of the vehicle and the observations, which are relative to the vehicle. A high accuracy increases the performance of data fusion, by assuring that the observed locations coming from observations from different vehicles and infrastructure match each other. Target accuracy can be reached by using RTK or similar satellite position enhancing technology.

Data throughput. According to 3GPP the peak data rate is up to 25 Mbps, which may occur in dense urban environments (up to (12000 vehicles/km²)[15]. This high number of vehicles will not be tested in the project. The data throughput in the tests, which will be performed is small, as CPMs are small messages (payload 50-300 bytes), transmitted every 100 ms, and only a few devices will be used in the tests.

End-to-end Latency is measured as the time between the transmission of a message and its reception by another car, measured at application level. The higher the latency, the higher the error between the measured vehicle and object location and the actual vehicle and object location. Both 3GPP and 5GAA set the target end-to-end at 10 ms [14][15].

Reliability. At application level, reliability is calculated from the amount of messages which is distributed in time. Messages are assumed outdated if they are not received within a specific time. The time is generally set to 100 ms, which is also the frequency of CPM transmission.

Table 6: Sensor Sharing KPIs

KPI category	KPI	target value
Localisation	positioning accuracy	< 0.1 m
Throughput	user perceived data rate	<= 0.01 Mbps
Latency	end-to-end communication latency (median)	< 20 ms
	end-to-end communication latency (95% percentile)	< 50 ms
Reliability	Reliability (% with end-to-latency < 100 ms)	99 %
Service continuity	Application level Handover success rate	100%
	Service interruption time	1 s
	RTK correction interruption time	0 s

Infrastructure Assisted Advanced Driving

This functionality employs the 5G networks and road infrastructure technologies to improve road users' safety and traffic efficiency in a cross-border environment. Based on ETSI specifications, the periodic broadcast of CPM, CAM, SPATEM, MAPEM messages supports connected and automated vehicles (CAV) while driving across the border. The functionality created through the messages exchange consider the attributes of vehicles, road infrastructure and detected objects. Attributes (e.g., vehicles speed, driving trajectories, signal phasing and timing, road/lane topology, traffic maneuverer, road obstacle information, etc.) used to support the navigation of CAVs, while improve the decision making of the road users involved on risky situations.

For infrastructure assisted advanced driving, relevant KPIs are:

Localisation accuracy: Typical positioning accuracy to confirm a traffic lane is 1.5 m [15]. This to create a shared understanding of the nearby road situation among the road users by informing them of their existence and actions.

End-to-end Latency: The time it takes for a message to travel from the sender to the receiver. Normal awareness messages (e.g., CAM, BSM) latency: 100 ms [15].

Reliability: Needs to reliably allow for trajectory calculation to avoid collisions. The required reliability is 99% [15].

Table 7: Infrastructure Assisted Advanced Driving KPIs

KPI category	KPI	target value
Localisation	Positioning accuracy	<1.5 m
Throughput	user perceived data rate	<= 0.01 Mbps
Latency	end-to-end communication latency (median)	< 50 ms
	end-to-end communication latency (95% percentile)	< 100 ms
Reliability	Reliability (% with end-to-latency < 100 ms)	99 %
Service continuity	Application-level Handover success rate	100%
	Service interruption time	1 s

Collision Warning with Mobile Roadwork Operation

This scenario considers safety related information where roadwork agents are in intervention, e.g., for maintenance of the road. In such condition, a vehicle from a road operator is slowly moving to delimit the roadwork area and warn other users of the dangerous situations. Connected and automated vehicles approaching from the other side of the border need to be informed and continuously updated as the situation changes.

For mobile roadwork warning, relevant KPIs are:

Localisation accuracy : The target accuracy of roadwork vehicle location is below 0.5m for collision avoidance scenario [15]. Target accuracy can be reached by using RTK or similar satellite position enhancing technology.

End-to-end Latency is measured as the time between the transmission of a message from CAM service and its reception by a connected vehicle, measured at application level. The higher the latency, the higher the error between the measured vehicle and roadwork event. 5GAA set the target service level latency at 100 ms, with recommended communication latency of 20ms for collision avoidance purpose [15].

Reliability. At application level, reliability is calculated from the amount of messages which is distributed in time. Messages are assumed outdated if they are not received within a specific time. The time is generally set to 100 ms, which is also the maximum frequency of CPM and DENM.

Table 8: Mobile roadwork warning KPIs

KPI category	KPI	target value
Localisation	positioning accuracy	< 0.5 m
Throughput	user perceived data rate	<= 0.01 Mbps
Latency	end-to-end communication latency (median)	< 20 ms
	end-to-end communication latency (95% percentile)	< 50 ms
Reliability	Reliability (% with end-to-latency < 100 ms)	99 %
Service continuity	Application level Handover success rate	100%
	Service interruption time	1 s
	RTK correction interruption time	0 s

4.1.3.2 Scenarios

Scenario 1: Simple Scenario for Service Interruption Testing

In the use case, the transmitted data are V2X data transmitted between vehicles. This consists of small data packages which are published by the UEs and received by the other vehicles and the enablers. The size of the messages is between 100 and 1500 bytes and they are transmitted up to 10 times per second. This type of data stream is also used in use case I.

The simple scenario for service interruption is the same to the V2X scenario in use case I.

Scenario 2: Full Use Case Scenario

The objective of this scenario is to assess the performance of 5G and the CAM Services Platform for informing vehicles on safety critical situations and to assist automated driven vehicles. In this case the V2X data is transmitted by either vehicles, the installed road infrastructure, or through roadwork equipment to vehicles in the area. This scenario is focused to enhance the situational awareness, safety and traffic efficiency of road users by providing information that may not be available through direct sensing of vehicles.

More information on the test scenarios will be provided in D4.1.

4.1.4 Use Case 4.1: 360° Immersive Multiuser Gaming on the Go

4.1.4.1 KPIs

In the 360° Immersive multiuser gaming on the go, users send their position information and actions to a server which collects this information and ensures the equity of the game and an enhanced user experience.

Localisation information is not critical for this use case.

Gaming clients transmit **localisation** information containing time, position and UE's orientation to a server and to the MQTT connected services (enablers) for the infrastructure monitoring. We assume that all the players are connected to a network providing the positioning data (in addition to the device position if available) with at least 5m of accuracy and timing accuracy of 50 ms. The experimental part of this use case will be carried out in 2 different contexts: Indoor and outdoor. In the first condition, due to the indoor location of the players, the position will be obtained by the network. In outdoor tests the position for every player will be contributed by the own player device. Both conditions require the same accuracy for this use case (~5m, ~50ms).

As the localisation data will be obtained at the same time of the localisation data of the vehicle that is carrying the players, the network and phone (GPS) localisation data will be compared and analysed taking as reference the more accurate data provided by the vehicles.

We will evaluate the **throughput** measuring directly both server and clients the incoming and outgoing data. The target throughput is 5 Mbps. The throughput will be tested adjusting several parameters.:

- Connected clients: The needed throughput will depend directly on the clients allowed on the server. Target is more than 10 clients connected;
- The message rate will depend on the framerate for the frames, and will be adaptable depending on test results. The target is 20 messages per second per device;
- Message size (for client download): When more clients connected, more throughput is needed as more data will be transmitted to each client.

The **Latency** is composed of:

- uplink network latency, i.e., the time for a message to reach the server: target 5 ms;
- processing and buffering time, i.e., the time to analyse the scene and ensure that all players are equally served: target 20 ms;
- downlink network latency, i.e., the time for the position to be sent to the other users: target 5 ms;
- the total round trip time target is hence 30 ms;

UC4.1 uses smartphones as UE, which have no technical possibilities to be synchronised with other equipment. Therefore the round trip time will be measured.

Reliability: The service is real time based. We will therefore measure the packet loss ratio at application level, with as target 0.5%.

The target for the **Service interruption time** is 0.5 seconds.

Table 9: 360 immersive multiuser gaming on the go KPIs

KPI category	KPI	target value
Throughput	User experienced data rate	> 5Mbps
Latency	Round-trip time	< 30 ms
Reliability	Packet data loss (%)	<0.5 %
Service Continuity	Application-level Handover success rate	100%
	Service interruption time	0.5 s
	CAM service instantiation time	30 s

4.1.4.2 Scenarios

Scenario 1: Simple Scenario for Service Interruption Testing

The scenario is similar to the simple scenario for video in use case I, and UC4.1 and UC4.2 have a common simple scenario. A major difference is that in this use case, UEs are used are smartphones (and laptop modems for UC4.2), which have not the advanced positioning possibilities from the UEs used in vehicles.

Scenario 2: Full Use Case Scenario

In this scenario, as introduced, users are located in a vehicle (car or ferry) which crosses the border. Users play an interactive game. The server collects all the data about the scene and interactions coming from the clients/players and broadcasts back to the clients the player position compensating the transmission delay between the players and all the details about the game scene (others players interactions) to create the common scene as requested by the collaborative engagement.

When crossing the border, the users will migrate from the instance of the game server in the first network to the second exploiting the data provided by the corresponding enabler.

4.1.5 Use Case 4.2: 3D Real-Time Virtual Collaboration on the Move

4.1.5.1 KPIs

In the 3D real time virtual collaboration on the go use case, mobile users are seated in a car or bus and assist to a remote real time 3D presentation. The 3D presentation is made by a fixed presenter located remotely. Mobile users take advantage of the high bandwidth of 5G networks to get high 3D video quality and interact with the presenter:

Localisation data employed to triggering the service relocation, not for use case performance.

The required **throughput** is the throughput to receive the video stream from the network. The higher the throughput, the better is the quality: target is 10 Mbps.

Service interruption time: target is 5 seconds.

Table 10 gives an overview of the KPIs.

Table 10: 3D Real time virtual collaboration on the move KPIs and targets

KPI category	KPI	target value
Throughput	User experienced data rate	> 10 Mbps
Latency	One way latency (video transmission)	< 1 s
Service continuity	Service interruption time	< 5 s
	Application-level Handover success rate	100%
	CAM service instantiation time	30 s

4.1.5.2 Scenarios

Scenario 1: Simple Scenario for Service Interruption Testing

The simple scenario is common with UC4.1, only a laptop with external modem is used instead of a smartphone as UE.

Scenario 2: Full Use Case Scenario

The test will be carried out outdoor (car or bus) employing the 5G Network capabilities and indoor (ship) exploiting the network provided by a base station installed providing data connection to the whole vessel (travelling passengers and goods). Users will stay in their seats on the moving vehicle. The presenter is located in a fixed location broadcasting the content through the network until the moving viewers. The content consists of high quality stereoscopic video that ensure the immersive experience.

The virtualized component in charge of distribute the video content to the viewers is instantiated on the core of the country where the travel starts. During the approach to the border the same component is re instantiated in the second network, and when the user cross the border, they connect to the new instance thanks to the data provided by the corresponding enabler.

4.2 Maritime Ecosystem

4.2.1 Use Case 5.1: Connected Logistics

4.2.1.1 KPIs

Connected logistics use case focuses on how to provide seamless connection for onboard devices and how this connectivity can be utilised for end user solutions and devices. Connected logistics covers two test themes: 1) vehicle-to-backend system connectivity and 2) cybersecurity health reporting. Theme 1 covers continuous connectivity between Transport Management Systems (TMS) and critical onboard systems, such as vehicle and/or driver health status and remote monitoring for cargo data for critical and secured transportations (CST). CST

basic requirement is uninterrupted situational awareness data, i.e., transportation needs to be monitored continuously via a remote control tower with video stream and other security sensors to ensure continuous shipment integrity.

Theme 2 utilizes new 5G capabilities and onboard devices, which can be used to track and monitor positioning metadata and deviations appearing therein. Such analysis can give information about cybersecurity threats and GNSS spoofing.

Both of these themes will follow the same test logic and KPIs, which focus on continuous 5G service availability and quality of service levels. During the trials these aspects will be tested in test drives with:

- service interruption e.g., for upload of cargo integrity data and cybersecurity health data
- service capacity point of view e.g., for surveillance camera uplink feed
- service quality

With the available test networks, the aim is to test and analyse service continuity in border crossing multi-MNO cases, which is a typical requirement for international logistics and end user solutions. Finally test results will be used to analyse the overall Service Quality Level, scalability and readiness for logistics end-user services.

Figure 7: Goods tracking test scenario – Ferry route

Localisation information (position and time) is based on standard GNSS + RTK which provides sufficient accuracy: The target positioning accuracy is 0.5 m.

Service continuity:

- coverage: the whole trip should be covered by communications (connection to commercial 5G network near the shore, multi-hop or satellite). The target is 98% of the trip.
- the service interruption time when switching from one radio network to another should be less than 0.5 seconds.

Table 11: Connected logistics KPIs

KPI category	KPI	target value
Localization	positioning accuracy	< 0.5 m
Throughput	Average throughput	> 15 Mbps
	Minimum throughput	> 10 Mbps
Latency	User perceived end-to-end latency: from video/sensor capture to video/sensor representation	< 250 ms
	communication end-to-end latency: from transmission at vehicle VCU to receipt back office system	< 100 ms
Reliability	Packet error rate (%)	< 1%
Service continuity	Coverage	> 98%
	Application level handover success rate	> 99%
	Service interruption time	< 0.5 s

4.2.1.2 Scenarios

In this test, a 5G microcellular base station is installed on a ferry and provides 5G access to vehicle OBUs and IoT terminals. This 5G base station is connected to the 5G core via terrestrial Radio Links (green) or a satellite connection (yellow). A satellite router (red) monitors the links and selects the best one to route the traffic. The radio link and satellite links are fully integrated in the 5G infrastructure, enabling the use of standard 5G IoT devices.

Throughput, latency, and reliability are measures. Localisation and capacity are estimated.

Figure 8: Satellite backhauling system Architecture

4.2.1 Use Case 5.2: Live video streaming between ferries and between ferry and harbour at cross border

This UC 5.2 is based on the following functionality:

1. Video information for situation awareness
2. Video streaming for live communication

In this use case, a video camera provides live streaming between the passengers, ferry staff and harbour's administration. The high throughput data send during the live streaming will be tested to check service continuity at a cross border. This use case is an eMBB case which it will be tested along with slicing to separate important information (captain to staff) from standard information (captain to harbour's administration).

4.2.1.1 KPIs

The perceived KPIs which are important for this use case are throughput, latency and service continuity as they are displayed in the following table.

Table 12: Live video streaming KPIs

KPI category	KPI	target value
Throughput	Avg throughput UL and DL	> 15 Mbps
	Min throughput UL and DL	> 5 Mbps
Latency	User perceived end-to-end latency: from video camera capture to video receiver representation	< 250 ms
Service Continuity	Application level handover success rate	> 99%
	Service interruption time	< 0.5 s

4.2.1.2 Scenarios

Scenario 1: Scenario to test the service interruption time with low quality video

In the simple case there will be video streaming of low quality between the captain and the harbour's administration. The data stream will be a few Mbytes and the service interruption time will be measure and evaluated.

Scenario 2: Scenario to test the service interruption time with high quality video

This is a full scenario where high-quality video will be sent between the captain and the ferry's staff. This video will be tens of Mbytes and the service interruption will have a high effect on the video. The interruption time will be measured, evaluated and compared to the one obtained from scenario 1.

5 Business Performance Assessment

The business validation process is challenged with engaging and examining the field trials with a commercial and business lens in order to identify those solutions that are most likely to become commercially viable and can deliver the most immediate quantifiable value to the stakeholders involved in each ecosystem. Business validation is comprised of commercialisation validation and business impact assessment.

The ultimate goal for the commercialisation validation process in WP5 is to create anticipatory business plans for two solutions, one for each of the two ecosystems, that extend 5G at different cross-border environments. A customer-focused, collaborative and iterative process has been designed that helps to guide the solution providers from initial ideas through to potential business impact and demonstrate how commercial actors supporting the ecosystems could move those outputs closer to commercial reality.

For the business impact assessment, we will work upon the defined two ecosystems (maritime and terrestrial), in order to collect the required data during stakeholder workshops and interviews. The collected data will be both quantitative (i.e., costs) and qualitative as reflected by the selected Multi-Actor Multi-Criteria Analysis (MAMCA) business criteria. The cost benefit analysis and business impact assessment will be formulated based on future penetration scenarios on the validated most promising business opportunities. The final outcome of T5.2 will be to deliver the estimated impact and cost-benefit for the developed ecosystems, validated by both internal and external to the project stakeholders. Furthermore, on the basis of the 5G Architecture and 5G CAM Infrastructure developed in the project, we will investigate the interoperability impact and deployment potential in close collaboration with the project technology providers.

The overall business evaluation methodology is described in D1.12 “Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results”.

Business KPIs have been defined to assess the 5G-ROUTES ecosystems from a business perspective. Business KPIs are obtained through quantitative and qualitative analyses based on ecosystem stakeholders and field trials (where applicable) input collected through surveys, questionnaires, interviews and through a thorough market study. The analysis and reporting of results will be performed in WP5 Commercialisation, Innovation Management and Standardisation and primarily under Task 5.1 (Business models development, marketing plan and sustainability) and Task 5.2 (Impact assessment and cost/benefit analysis), whereas Task 5.4 (Standardisation contribution and spectrum allocation recommendations) will collect the necessary data related to standardisation. In addition, key technical indicators, such as ecosystem maturity and obsolescence will be retrieved from the technical KPIs collected in Section 3 of this report, as well as from the project Innovation Management (Task 5.3).

Business KPIs are classified in 4 groups:

- Technological
- Impact assessment
- Financial
- Commercial

The following sections detail the business KPIs.

5.1 Technological KPIs

The technological KPIs are associated with the risk of using a particular technology. This input will be provided by the ecosystem stakeholders, through the technical assessment during the field trials.

Table 13: Technological KPIs relevant for business evaluation.

Technological	MyUseCaseID	MyUseCaseDescription	
	Performance Indicators	Green	Red
	Maturity / TRL	> 7	< 4
Obsolescence	Low	High	

5.1.1 Maturity / TRL (Innovation management and solution leaders)

The maturity of the technology is measured by a Technological Readiness Level which is defined on a scale of 1 (low) to 9 (high). Specifically:

- TRL 1 – basic principles observed
- TRL 2 – technology concept formulated
- TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept
- TRL 4 – technology validated in lab
- TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
- TRL 6 – technology demonstrated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
- TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in operational environment
- TRL 8 – system complete and qualified
- TRL 9 – actual system proven in operational environment (competitive manufacturing in the case of key enabling technologies; or in space)

5.1.2 Obsolescence (Innovation Management)

The Obsolescence performance indicator is the risk that the technology becomes obsolete. There are several means to cope with obsolescence; from investing in a new technology to investing in spare parts. The indicator is a three-level value; low, medium, high risk. This input will be provided by T5.3 (Innovation, data management and IPR activities).

5.2 Impact assessment KPIs

5.2.1 Benefit-Cost Ratio (BCR)

The ratio between discounted economic benefits and costs. The BCR value range is presented in Table 14 below. This value will be calculated within the framework of T5.2.

Table 14: Benefit-Cost ratio values and generic interpretation.

BCR Value Range	Generic Interpretation
BCR < 1	“No Go” criterion: The costs exceed the benefits, therefore the value proposition is generating losses.
BCR = 1	“Equilibrium point” criterion: The costs are equal to the benefits, therefore the value proposition may proceed with low viability
BCR > 1	“Go” criterion: The benefits exceed the costs and therefore the value proposition should proceed.

5.2.2 Penetration Rate

This is the ration between the number of users expected to buy or use this product or service to the total population targeted. This value will be assessed in T5.1 and used in T5.2 to create the impact scenarios for the business impact assessment.

The calculation of the penetration rate is performed via the following formula:

$$\text{Penetration rate (PR) (\%)} = (\text{number of customers} \div \text{target market}) \times 100$$

For the 5G-Routes ecosystems we will need to consider both the penetration rates of the 5G equipped vehicles (PRV) and of the 5G infrastructure (PRI). Thus, the rate of 5G technology usage over CCAM is calculated by: **PRV*PRI**

The input is not expected from the trials but rather from the thorough market study performed in T5.1.

5.3 Financial KPIs

The financial KPI is used to assess the financial risk associated to each use case. Those will be calculated within the context of T5.1.

Four performance indicators are defined:

Table 15: Financial KPI

	MyUseCaseID	MyUseCaseDescription	
	Performance Indicators	Green	Red
Financial	CAPEX per year	< 5 M€	> 10 M€
	OPEX per year	< 1 M€	> 2 M€
	Revenues per year	> 10 M€	< 5 M€
	ROI	> 20%	< 10%

An example for a telecom infrastructure is detailed below:

Table 16: Telecom Investment example

year	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
CAPEX	50	45	40	35	30	25	20	15	10	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
OPEX	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	15	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
Revenues	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50

5.3.1 CAPEX per Year

The Capital Expenditure is the amount of money that is invested every year to build the system. It is generally high at the network launch and decreases over the years with the maturity of the system. The MAX CAPEX value over the lifetime may have an impact on the time to deploy a system. This value will be calculated in T5.1.

5.3.2 OPEX per Year

The Operational Expenditure is the amount of money that is spent to operate the system. It is generally constant during the first years of the network and increases with the obsolescence of the system. The MAX OPEX over the lifetime may have an impact on the system deployment and lifetime. This value will be calculated in T5.1.

5.3.3 Revenues per Year

The revenues are the revenues that are produced by the system. They are generally low at the commercial opening of the network and increase with the market penetration. The MIN, MAX and AVERAGE revenues per year over the life time can be used to assess the optimum functioning point of the system and are key to compute the ROI. This value will be calculated in T5.1.

5.3.4 ROI

Return on investment (ROI) is a metric used to understand the profitability of an investment. The ROI must be computed over the lifetime of the system, taking CAPEX and OPEX into account. It is the ratio between Revenues

and cost of the network. This value will be calculated within the framework of T5.2, based on the data retrieved in T5.1 (CAPEX, OPEX, Revenues).

Table 17. Example of ROI computation

CAPEX	305
OPEX	245
Revenues	695
ROI	26%

5.4 Commercial KPIs

Commercial performance indicators represent different elements to take into account regarding the commercialization of the system.

Table 18 : Commercial KPIs

Commercial	MyUseCaseID	MyUseCaseDescription	
	Performance Indicators	Green	Red
	Standardisation	high	low
	Time to Market	< 1 year	> 3 years
	Existence of Alternative Solution	NO	YES
	Opportunities	YES	NO

5.4.1 Standardisation

Standardisation has an important impact on the market penetration. The use/existence of standardized solution favours the market adoption. Both interoperability as well as contribution to standards for CCAM and 5G Network will be considered. The standardisation performance indicator is expressed as high, medium or low. Standardisation opportunities and barriers will be assessed and measured in T5.4. The business impact of standardisation on market penetration will be analysed in T5.1.

5.4.2 Time to Market

Time to Market represents the time necessary to offer a commercial system. It includes the time to develop the technology, associated products and should be as small as possible. The Time to Market performance indicator is expressed in years. This value will be calculated in T5.1.

5.4.3 Existence of Alternative Solutions

The existence of alternative solutions, cheaper or more performant, could threaten a business case. This indicator evaluates the risk that other solutions perform better than the proposed one. The assessment of the available alternative solutions is dealt with in T5.3 (Innovation Management) and further utilised in T5.1.

5.4.4 Opportunities

The opportunity performance indicator is representative of the opportunities to develop a market around a technology or ecosystem. It is in general evaluated by the stakeholders. The opportunities will be assessed: a) from the thorough market study that will be performed in T5.1, and, b) through the SWOT analysis that will be performed through stakeholders' (internal and external) interviews within the framework of T5.2.

5.4.5 Deployment Time

Time to deployment of the 5G-ROUTES Terrestrial and Maritime ecosystems in relation to EC 5G Action Plan[22] and STRIA Roadmap for CAT [23]. Deployment Scenarios: Short (2025), Medium (2030), Long (>2030). Relevant

trials input: Ecosystem maturity (TRL), Technology integration and coverage options (if any) through surveys with ecosystem stakeholders within the framework of T5.1.

6 Conclusion and Recommendation for Future Work

5G networks will bring a significant improvement to the cellular offer, enabling to deploy new services that cannot be offered by state-of-the-art 4G networks. In addition, the interconnection and the integration of satellite networks will increase the reliability and extend the coverage of terrestrial networks.

In D1.1, we analysed 5G network services and architecture, including both terrestrial and satellite systems. We analysed the requirements of the 5G-ROUTES use cases and showed that our use cases cover the three 5G categories defined by ITU-R: eMBB, URLLC, mMTC. A particular attention was given to CAM use cases which impose high constraints in terms of mobility, latency and reliability, personal communication use cases which take advantage of higher data rates offered on 5G networks and logistics use cases which can benefit of an over sea coverage using satellites.

In D1.9 the KPIs for the different use case and the main test scenarios are defined.

Due to the change of the focus of the project in 2021-2023, the use cases have been organised in two different ecosystems: the maritime and the terrestrial ecosystem. The focus will be on the assessment of the 5G network and the solutions developed in the 5G-ROUTES project. The technical KPIs are grouped under 5 categories:

- Throughput
- Latency
- Reliability
- Localisation
- Service continuity

This deliverable describes the KPIs and their target values for the different use cases. For the terrestrial ecosystem, a set of harmonised KPIs and target values has been defined, in order to assess the capabilities of 5G networks. The tests scenarios are defined at a generic level, more detailed information will be provided in D4.1. A detailed description of the data collection procedures is described in D1.12.

4 business KPI categories have been selected to evaluate the use cases from a business perspective:

- Technological
- Impact assessment
- Financial
- Commercial

The business evaluation methodology is described in D1.12 “Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results”. The results of the business evaluation are dealt with in the deliverables produced under WP5 Commercialisation, Innovation Management and Standardisation.

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